

Effects of Aquatic Therapy in Individual with Low Back Pain – A Literature Review

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Abstract

Low back pain (LBP) is a common condition that has a significant impact on people's quality of life and productivity. In recent years, aquatic therapy has emerged as a potential non-invasive technique aimed at improving disability and decreasing pain intensity, making it a popular choice in rehabilitation settings. This literature review seeks to assess the effectiveness of aquatic therapy for reducing disability and pain to provide insights that can guide clinical practice while promoting better outcomes for patients, especially in preventing LBP. The review follows PRISMA guidelines, involving a comprehensive search of randomized controlled trials published between January 2014 and July 2024 across databases such as PEDro, PubMed, and Google Scholar. To ensure the quality of the studies included, the PEDro scale was used to evaluate the risk of bias. The initial search across two databases yielded 25 articles, of which 2 were duplicates and excluded. Applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 9 articles were selected. Full-text access was acquired for 5 of these articles. After assessing eligibility, 2 articles were deemed suitable for inclusion. Consequently, the study utilized a total of 2 articles. Findings suggest that aquatic therapy may contribute to reducing low back pain and disability in LBP patients. Some studies show the superiority of aquatic therapy over other modalities, while other studies show minimal differences compared to other exercise or control groups. While further research, especially with larger sample sizes and standardized protocols, is recommended to support this evidence, the current findings suggest potential benefits of aquatic therapy. Overall, aquatic therapy can be an effective intervention to reduce disability and pain, and overall improve quality of life if applied correctly and for an adequate period of time.

Keywords: aquatic therapy, individual, low back pain

INTRODUCTION

Low back pain (LBP) can be defined as pain between the lower edge of the rib cage, back, and buttocks. It can affect anyone, from children to the elderly, and can occur over a short period of time (acute), slightly longer (sub-acute), or over a long period of time (chronic). LBP is a common condition that has a significant impact on a person's quality of life and productivity, as it makes movement difficult and can affect mental health. There are two types of LBP: specific LBP or non-specific LBP. Specific LBP is pain that results from a specific disease, structural problems in the spine such as discs, ligaments or muscles, and when the pain radiates to other parts of the body. Most (85%) causes of LBP are non-specific due to soft tissue abnormalities such as ligament muscle

injury, spasm, or muscle fatigue. Other specific causes include spinal fractures, infections, and tumors. Research shows that LBP is caused by a variety of factors, including mechanical problems, psychological stress, and lifestyle choices. The load on the spine and pressure on the discs and spinal structures can increase when a person is overweight, resulting in herniation of the cartilaginous lumbar discs. Weight is one example of lifestyle. The more irregular the lifestyle with a disability, the higher the incidence of obesity. This has the consequence of increasing the risk of LBP or other diseases.¹

In work factors, body position is very important because incorrect body position from normal body position while working can increase the amount of energy needed, causing the energy that

must be given to the muscles to be inefficient, easily causing fatigue.² LBP is usually the most common reason for consulting a doctor in the United States as much as 1% of the US population is chronically disabled due to back pain and the cost of back pain care in America is \$20 to \$50 billion per year.³ In 2020, 619 million people around the world will be affected by LBP and it is estimated that cases will increase to 843 million cases by 2050.⁴ In Indonesia, the prevalence of LBP in medical personnel is estimated to be between 7.6% to 37%.⁵

Patients with LBP receive a variety of treatments to improve function, reduce pain, and increase quality of life. Clinically, surgery, medication, and physiotherapy are commonly used to relieve the symptoms associated with LBP. Studies have shown that physical exercise is the best non-surgical treatment for LBP, that effective for improving function, reducing pain, increasing strength, flexibility, mood, and decreasing depression.^{6,7} Aquatic exercise or hydrotherapy is a treatment that fits these recommendations, involving resistance, flexibility, and mobilization techniques. Aquatic therapy is carried out in water, the properties of water that cause resistance produce relaxation, reduce pressure on the injured joint, and cause a feeling of happiness, which can reduce pain and improve function in chronic non-specific LBP.⁸

Aquatic therapy decreases the axial load on the spine, provides greater resistance to movement compared to land exercise, maybe a safe environment even in the acute stage, and decreases kinesiophobia.⁹ This literature review aims to assess in depth the effectiveness of aquatic therapy or hydrotherapy for individuals with LBP. By reviewing the relevant literature, it is hoped that this review will provide greater insight into the benefits of aquatic therapy in the management of LBP and provide

evidence-based recommendations for clinical practitioners.

METHOD

The literature review involved searching journal databases like the Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) and PubMed/MEDLINE. The search strategy utilized keywords such as 'aquatic therapy' AND 'back pain'. The PICO sets are, P: low back pain, I: aquatic therapy, C: -, O: functional status.

The inclusion criteria for this literature review include (1) articles with a randomized controlled trial (RCT) research design; (2) Articles written in English; (3) Articles must have been published in the last 5 years (January 2020 - July 2024). Exclusion criteria include: (1) duplicate articles were excluded, (2) case reports, abstracts, conference proceedings, or thesis were excluded.

Data extraction was carried out by three separate reviewers (NPDAP and MHSN), and any discrepancies were settled through discussion. The study characteristics gathered included: (A) author information; (B) participant attributes such as age, gender, and sample size; (C) intervention dosage; and (D) outcome variables, with a focus on functional status parameters.

The risk of bias was assessed using a PEDro scale reviewed by three independent reviewers (NPDAP and MHSN) and any disagreements were resolved by discussion.

RESULT

The initial search across two databases yielded 25 articles, of which 2 were duplicates and excluded. Applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 9 articles were selected. Full-text access was acquired for 5 of these articles. After assessing eligibility, 2 articles were deemed suitable for inclusion. Consequently, the study utilized a total of 2 articles. An explanation of study

selection is described in Figure 1. Explanation concerning the quality assessment in regards to the journals, is described in Table 1. The summary characteristics of the study results used in this review and characteristics of the interventions are summarized in Table 2. All

group; the intervention which was used in these studies was aquatic therapy to improve disability, and the control group was given physical therapy modalities and aquatic exercise (AQE) + deep-water running (DWR).^{9,11} Intervention duration ranged from 9 weeks⁹ to 12 weeks.¹¹ A total of 18 to 24 exercise sessions were performed twice a week.

studies included in the randomised controlled trial (RCT) compared the effects of the intervention with a control

Figure 1. Flow Chart of Identification of Studies

Table 1. The methodological quality of included studies using the PEDro Scale.¹⁰

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total Score

Peng, et al., 2022	-	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	√	√	√	8/10
Carvalho, et al., 2020	-	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	-	√	√	7/10

For aquatic therapy, the temperature will be adjusted to 27.5°C of the environment and 30°C of water to 142 elicit the same cardiac response in the air and the water. The swimming pool used for all interventions had dimensions of 20m x 6m and a depth of 1.3-1.5m.^{9,11}

The physical therapy modalities were TENS and infrared heat therapy. Participants received TENS with a current frequency of 120Hz and pulse width of 100µs.⁹

For the DWR exercise, the participants were instructed to use the floats on the feet and trunk, then simulate running forward in the water, holding the EVA dumbbell accessory using their hands to facilitate exercise performance. The Rating of Perceived Exertion (RPE)

scale was used to assess the intensity of DWR (week 1 to 2: 11 RPE moderate intensity; week 3 to 9: 15 RPE vigorous intensity).¹¹

The studies aimed to assess the tools used to evaluate the effectiveness of aquatic therapy in treating LBP across various individuals, with aquatic therapy as the primary intervention and other interventions as the control. The Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ), which contains 24 items closely related to the activities of daily living of patients with LBP, was used for the primary outcome in both studies. The scores are as follows 1 for checking 'YES' and 0 for checking 'NO'. The final score ranges from 0 to 24. Higher scores are associated with greater disability.^{9,11}

Table 2. Characteristics of reviewed studies describing the efficacy of aquatic therapy in individual with back pain

Author	Subjects	Intervention	Control/Comparison	Outcome Measure	Results
(Peng, et al., 2022) ¹¹	N= 113 Age range 18-65 years Gender= 59 Women and 54 Men	Participants in the therapeutic aquatic exercise group started the exercise with a 10-minute active warm-up session. Then, for 40 minutes they performed an aquatic session and 10 minutes for a cool-down session.	The physical therapy modalities group received transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) and infrared ray thermal therapy was focused on pain points, each had a duration of 30 minutes.	Primary outcomes: Disability was measured with the Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ), Secondary outcomes: - Numeric Rating Scale (NRS)	Aquatic exercise group showed improvement in disability by an additional -1.77 points after the 3-month intervention, - 2.42 points at 6 months, and - 3.61 points at the 12-month follow-up (p<.001).

13-point Borg scale of perceived exertion (RPE). Both programs lasted 12 weeks. They were delivered 60 minutes for twice a week, total treatment was 24 sessions.

- The self-rating anxiety scale (SAS)
- Short-form Health Survey (SF-36)
- The Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS)
- Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI)
- The Pain Anxiety Symptoms Scale (PASS)
- Basis of the global perceived effect (GPE).
- Minimal clinically important difference (MCID)
- Adverse events were collected from participant's daily record forms.
- The participant's recommendation levels on the intervention that they received were classified as highly recommended, recommend, unclear, not recommended, and strongly deprecated.

(Carvalho, et al., 2020) ⁹	N= 54 Age range= 20-60 years	Participants attended a total of 18 sessions (2 sessions a	The aquatic exercise (AQE) + deep-water running (DWR) group	Primary outcomes: Disability was assessed with the	The addition of aerobic exercise (AQE+DWR)
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BMI < 40kg/m² week for 9 weeks). The intervention for the aquatic exercise (AQE) group was a 40-minute individual session. The orientation/application was carried out by five licensed physiotherapists and one physical education teacher, all with expertise in AQE. comprised a 1-hour individual session (AQE therapy plus 20 minutes of DWR). Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ) was superior to AQE only for the lumbar pain intensity outcome at the end of treatment (P=0.003)

Secondary outcomes:

- Lumbar pain was measured with a visual analogue scale (VAS)
- Functional capacity was assessed using a 6-minute walk test (6MWT).

DISCUSSION

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of aquatic therapy for individuals with LBP. From Table 2, there are two articles that have been reviewed that present various training methods, doses, and their relationship in providing beneficial effects on functional status in individuals with LBP.

Aquatic therapy or hydrotherapy is a physiotherapy treatment for a variety of conditions such as chronic and subacute LBP. Hydrotherapy is defined as aquatic therapy for individuals to improve musculoskeletal and neuromuscular function, delivered and supervised by qualified personnel, optimally in a purpose-built hydrotherapy pool. The effects of water's unique properties (buoyancy, resistance, flow, and turbulence) allow movements to be performed that are normally difficult or impossible on the land, reducing the risk of falls.¹²

A study investigates the implementation of a 3-month intervention trial and 12-month follow-up of therapeutic aquatic exercise compared with physical therapy modalities for

chronic LBP. This study found that for patients with chronic LBP, therapeutic aquatic exercise was a more effective treatment than physical therapy modalities on pain intensity, quality of life, sleep quality, kinesiophobia, and fear avoidance. Aquatic therapy also had a long-term effect for up to 12 months.¹¹

Other study found that combining aquatic exercise (AQE) and deep-water running (DWR) more effectively to reduce the LBP at the end of the intervention. Treatment with DWR when compared to AQE was more effective in the short term for pain reduction, but after 9 weeks of treatment or after 3 months of follow-up it was not effective for disability and functional capacity.⁹

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the literature review points to aquatic therapy as a potentially effective non-invasive method for improving functional status in individuals with LBP. However, the effectiveness of aquatic therapy depends on the application method and additional exercises. Although one study found no significant difference between aquatic therapy

compared to a combination of aquatic therapy and deep-water running, aquatic therapy was found to be more effective in reducing pain and long-term disability. Therefore, the hypothesis of this study is supported, but further research is needed to determine the ideal method and duration of aquatic therapy use.

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